

D5.5 MEDIA LITERACY TOOLS

Assessing Media Literacy in the EU: A Comparative
Analysis of Member States

UK/D5.5

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Table of Contents

<i>List of Abbreviations</i>	4
<i>Acknowledgements</i>	5
<i>About the Project</i>	6
<i>Executive Summary/Abstract</i>	7
1. Introduction	8
2. E.U. Guidelines and National Reports	9
2.1 Guideline Key Points	11
2.2 National reports submitted by member states 2020-2022: Guideline Key Points	13
2.3. Summary of section two.....	23
3. Evaluation of Nonformal Education Tools:	23
3.1 Comparative Analysis: Thematic Points in the EU General Guide vs. Salto Country Reports	24
3.3 Interconnection between youth participation and MIL projects	28
3.4. Assessing the response of the youth sector with the financial backing of the EU	Error!
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3.5. Evaluating the facets of Media and Information Literacy (MIL) concerning D.Rad nations in addressing the perils linked with online radicaliation.....	32
5. Assessing the Impact of EU Media Literacy Directive and Informal Tools on Online Digital Identity and Radicalisation: Comparative report of findings from D.5.5, D6.2 and D7.1	40
6. Conclusion: Evaluating Successes and Pinpointing Areas for Improvement	42
7. References and Sources	45

List of Abbreviations

AVMSD	Audio-Visual Media Services Directive
EDAP	European Democracy Action Plan
EDMO	European Digital Media Observatory
ESC	European Corps
EU	European Union
MAAP	Media & Audio-Visual Action Plan
MIL	Media & Information Literacy
PMI	Performance Measurement Indicators

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About the Project

D.Rad is a comparative study of radicalisation and polarisation in Europe and beyond. It aims to identify the actors, networks, and wider social contexts driving radicalisation, particularly among young people in urban and peri-urban areas. D.Rad conceptualises this through the I-GAP spectrum (injustice-grievance-alienation-polarisation) with the goal of moving towards measurable evaluations of de-radicalisation programmes. Our intention is to identify the building blocks of radicalisation, which include a sense of being victimised; a sense of being thwarted or lacking agency in established legal and political structures; and coming under the influence of “us vs them” identity formulations.

D.Rad benefits from an exceptional breadth of backgrounds. The project spans national contexts including the UK, France, Italy, Germany, Poland, Hungary, Finland, Slovenia, Bosnia, Serbia, Kosovo, Israel, Iraq, Jordan, Turkey, Georgia, Austria, and several minority nationalisms. It bridges academic disciplines ranging from political science and cultural studies to social psychology and artificial intelligence. Dissemination methods include D.Rad labs, D.Rad hubs, policy papers, academic workshops, visual outputs and digital galleries. As such, D.Rad establishes a rigorous foundation to test practical interventions geared to prevention, inclusion and de-radicalisation.

With the possibility of capturing the trajectories of teen nations and several minority nations, the project will provide a unique evidence base for the comparative analysis of law and policy as nation states adapt to new security challenges. The process of mapping these varieties and their link to national contexts will be crucial in uncovering strengths and weaknesses in existing interventions. Furthermore, D.Rad accounts for the problem that processes of radicalisation often occur in circumstances that escape the control and scrutiny of traditional national frameworks of justice. The participation of AI professionals in modelling, analysing and devising solutions to online radicalisation will be central to the project’s aims.

Executive Summary/Abstract

The purpose of this report, titled "Media Literacy in EU Member States," assesses the effectiveness of media literacy initiatives across EU nations, as outlined in the [European Commission's Media Literacy Guidelines](#). These guidelines, issued in accordance with Article 33a(3) of the Audio-visual Media Services Directive (AVMSD), require member states to provide reports on their media literacy efforts. The report analyses eight of the [national reports submitted by member states](#) for the period of 2020-2022, namely D.Rad countries, Austria, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Poland, and Slovenia. Furthermore, the report examines non-formal educational tools developed and utilised in youth work, particularly those funded through European programs such as Erasmus+ and the European Solidarity Corps youth programmes. The objective of the report is to gauge each country's adherence to the Commission's guidelines and to assess the response of the youth sector, supported by EU funding. The report highlights areas of progress as well as areas that require improvement or further attention. Report objectives encompass several key aspects: firstly, to assess the degree to which member states have implemented the EU's media literacy guidelines; secondly, to evaluate and assess the non-formal educational tools on media literacy specifically tailored for youth workers within the youth sector, aiming for application in youth centres; and thirdly, to pinpoint exemplary practices as well as areas requiring enhancement across the European Union. Special attention is given to evaluating nonformal education tools utilised in youth work, with a particular emphasis on those listed on the SALTO Youth site. Data from official national reports and informal educational resources were consolidated to assess compliance, while a comparative framework was devised to analyse and contrast the initiatives of various member states. The report offers insights into EU media literacy, highlighting both progress and challenges. It also outlines tools developed for youth by or for youth workers, enhancing understanding of media literacy's importance in fostering informed and critical societies within the EU.

The report will be public and adherence to ethical standards and data privacy regulations will be ensured.

1. Introduction

As children increasingly engaged with digital media, concerns about its harmful effects grew evident¹. This prompted the formal establishment of a new discipline known as Media Information Literacy. (MIL)². Media literacy is a fundamental skill set that empowers individuals to critically engage with the vast array of information presented to them through various media channels. It encompasses the ability to dissect and evaluate what one hears, reads, and observes with objectivity and discernment. This proficiency extends beyond mere consumption; it involves actively questioning and interpreting data from diverse viewpoints, thereby fostering a deeper understanding of complex issues. In today's information age, where a multitude of sources compete for attention, media literacy serves as a crucial tool for navigating the digital landscape. With an abundance of information available at our fingertips, the capacity to think critically is vital: it enables individuals to sift through the noise, distinguishing between reliable facts and misinformation or bias. By honing these skills, individuals can confidently identify trustworthy sources, making informed decisions and ultimately, contribute to a more informed society.

UNESCO³ defines MIL skills as....

“a set of competencies that empowers citizens to access, retrieve, understand, evaluate and use, to create as well as share information and media content in all formats, using various tools, in a critical, ethical and effective way, in order to participate and engage in personal, professional and societal activities” (UNESCO, 2013, p. 151)

D.Rad recognises that individuals who possess media literacy skills are equipped to make informed decisions. They have the tools necessary to comprehend the essence

¹ <http://globalkidsonline.net/>

² <https://participationpool.eu/resource-category/information-critical-thinking/>

³ United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.: <https://www.unesco.org/en>

of various content and services, and are therefore, able to harness the full spectrum of opportunities presented by various communication technologies and protect themselves and their families from detrimental or illegal content. In recent years, new concepts, such as radicalisation and extremism have been added to previous MIL educational concepts including, but not limited to, hate speech, disinformation, and cyber bullying⁴. Within the context of deradicalisation, and as emphasised in the Commission Guidance on Enhancing the Code of Practice on Disinformation⁵ - and also discussed in D.Rad reports D5.1, D6.2 and D7.1, media literacy emerges as a vital tool against the dissemination of misinformation by allowing users to examine information sources critically and discern false or misleading content.

The purpose of this D.Rad report is to a) comprehend the degree to which each country adheres to the guidelines outlined by the commission and b) to identify good practice and areas in need of improvement across the EU, and c) assess the range of media and information literacy (MIL) across D.Rad countries in confronting the risks associated with online radicalisation. The report will also outline areas of advancement and areas where improvements are needed.

2. E.U. Guidelines and National Reports

The EU guidelines state that individuals who possess media and information literacy skills are equipped to make informed decisions, comprehend the intricacies of content and services, and fully capitalise on the array of opportunities presented by diverse communication technologies. These skills enable them to protect themselves and their families from exposure to harmful or illegal content effectively. Furthermore, media and information literacy serve as a powerful tool in combating the dissemination of disinformation by enabling users to critically evaluate information sources, thus detecting false or deceptive content, as outlined in the Commission Guidance on

⁴ Media and Information Literacy – What’s Trending? [Media and Information Literacy - What’s Trending? - SALTO \(participationpool.eu\)](#)

⁵ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/code-practice->

Strengthening the Code of Practice on Disinformation⁶. Ultimately, media literacy empowers individuals to engage in a more open and informed democratic dialogue. The European Democracy Action Plan (EDAP)⁷ and the Media and Audio-visual Action Plan (MAAP)⁸ both emphasise the vital importance of enhancing media literacy skills. Recognising the evolving digital landscape, these initiatives prioritise the strengthening of digital skills, including digital and media literacy. Within the framework of the Digital Education Action Plan⁹, fostering these skills is identified as a strategic priority. This emphasis reflects the acknowledgment of the critical role media literacy plays in empowering individuals to navigate the digital era effectively and participate meaningfully in democratic processes.

Media literacy goes beyond just knowing how to use media tools and technologies; it involves developing critical thinking skills necessary for making informed judgments, navigating complex situations, and differentiating between personal opinions and factual information. Therefore, it is crucial for European communities, along with media service providers, video-sharing platform providers, and in collaboration with all relevant stakeholders, to prioritise the holistic advancement of media literacy across all levels of society. As stipulated by the guidelines, this endeavour must be inclusive, reaching people of all ages and spanning various forms of media consumption.

Furthermore, the promotion of media information literacy should not be viewed as a static endeavour but rather as an ongoing process. Continuous efforts are necessary to adapt to evolving media landscapes and emerging challenges, including those arising from interactive media and software app usage¹⁰. Regular monitoring and evaluation mechanisms are encouraged to gauge progress, identify areas for improvement, and ensure that media literacy initiatives remain effective and relevant in addressing contemporary issues such as misinformation, digital manipulation, and online safety concerns. By fostering a young population equipped with robust media literacy skills, societies can foster informed citizens capable of actively participating in

⁶ COM(2021) 262 final.

⁷ <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/carriage/european-democracy-action-plan/report?sid=7701>

⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0784&from=EN>

⁹ <https://education.ec.europa.eu/focus-topics/digital-education/action-plan>

¹⁰ <https://participationpool.eu/resource/media-and-information-literacy-whats-trending/>

democratic processes and responsibly engaging with the ever-expanding digital world. Guidelines regarding the implementation of Article 33a(3) of the Audio-visual Media Services Directive¹¹, outline the parameters for initiatives aimed at promoting and enhancing media and information literacy skills. Member States, in collaboration with media service providers, video-sharing platforms, and all relevant stakeholders, must promote the widespread development of media literacy across all segments of society and age groups, and continuous monitoring of this progress in this endeavour is paramount.

2.1 Guideline Key Points¹²

For the purposes of this report, D.Rad conducted a summarised analysis of the Media Literacy Guidelines and comparative national reports submitted by European member states. The Media Literacy guidelines advise that each section of national reports should present a list, along with brief descriptions whenever possible, of measures, arrangements, activities, and developments. These descriptions should, where possible, highlight key elements such as objectives, target audiences, implementation methods, and, if available, outcomes. Whenever feasible, the reports should reference information sources, such as relevant websites, even if they are only accessible in national languages.

Main key points from the media literacy guidelines:

- a) **Legal and/or policy measures:** main areas of focus - Legislative Reporting; Policy Measures; Platform provider obligations; the appropriateness of media literacy measures (see Audiovisual Media Services Directive article 33a(1)); to promote and take measures to develop media literacy skills.
- b) **Organisational Measures:** main areas of focus - Organisational Responsibilities; Stakeholder Cooperation; Clarification of Responsibility
- c) **Public funding and other media literacy financing arrangements:** main areas of focus - Financial Resource Allocation; Budget Transparency; Funding Mechanisms.
- d) **Engagement and awareness raising activities, including media literacy curricula:** main areas of focus – to promote and develop media literacy skills across all age groups, both in formal education and in lifelong learning contexts;

¹¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02010L0013-20181218>

¹² Media Literacy Guidelines. Section III. point 2. Sections of the reports.

to establish communication channels with the national hubs of the European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO); design measures to promote and develop media literacy skills in formal educational curricula at different levels – including modules for teacher training; make reference to any relevant media literacy resources available to the public.

- e) **Evaluation Measures and Methods:** main areas of focus – Implement measures to evaluate the impact of regional or national media initiatives; focus on Performance Measurement Indicators (PMI); Reporting Requirement (measures and impact); Document outcomes (to share best practice)¹³. Member States also have the option to employ recognised evaluation frameworks in order to measure media literacy levels¹⁴.

Each available report from the relevant D.Rad countries (Austria, Finland, Germany, Italy, Poland and Slovenia) underwent examination to assess the extent to which member states have implemented the key points from the media literacy guidelines established by the EU. These reports showcase a diverse range of approaches, displaying some discrepancies in content, structure, and interpretation of the guidelines. While some reports focus on highlighting policy measures taken, others provide accounts of case study content and impact, offering insight into the practical application of media literacy initiatives within each country's context. Such variations underscore the complexity of implementing media literacy strategies across different socio-political landscapes and perhaps highlight the need for tailored approaches to address specific challenges and opportunities in each region (see 2.2: table 1).

¹³ Members states are also encouraged to share and exchange information and best practice in the context of ERGA (European Regulators Group for Audiovisual Media Services <https://erga-online.eu/>)

¹⁴ Such frameworks include the “Study on Assessment Criteria for Media Literacy Levels: A comprehensive view of the concept of media literacy and an understanding of how media literacy levels in Europe should be assessed” (Paolo Celot, 2009) <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/115550fe-a89f-4086-82e5-c7573e26c38a>

2.2 National reports submitted by member states 2020-2022: Guideline Key Points

The ideal submission of reports consists of five sections, a-e (see section 2.1). The guidelines stipulate that sections a. and b. must contain *specified information*, whereas sections c., d., and e. should endeavour to describe *relevant measures* to the best of their capability. Member States are also urged to incorporate any additional pertinent information they consider necessary for the report (see column (f) in table 1.).

The symbols assigned to each country/guide section signify the following:

Fully specified ✓ / Partially specified ○ / not included ✗

Table 1 *National reports submitted by member states 2020-2022: Guideline Key Points*

D.Rad Countries	a) Legal and/or policy measures	b) Organisational Measures	c) Public funding and other media literacy financing arrangements	d) Engagement and awareness raising activities, including media literacy curricula	e) Evaluation Measures and Methods	f) Other key areas of interest (Give detail)
Austria	○ an amendment was introduced to the Communications Austria Federal Law	○ a service centre was included in the broadcasting regulation agency.	✓	✓ a good practice is the introduction of basic digital education by the Ministry of Education, Science and Research. Basic	○ due to lack of financial resources.	Basic digital education is implemented in the 5th to 8th school level with at least one fixed period in the timetable, resulting in a total of at least four periods per week over the

				digital education is implemented in the 5th to 8th school level with at least one fixed period in the timetable, resulting in a total of at least four periods per week over the course of lower secondary level.		course of lower secondary level. Digital skills are also anchored into the primary-school curriculum.
FRANCE	<p>✓The original law dates back to the 1986 legislation on freedom of communication. There have been three new legislations introduced since then to fight against manipulation, hate content on the internet, as well as</p>	<p>✓The centre for media and information education (CLEMI) is a partner of those that play a role with audio-visual actors from education material on media and information. Also tv channels have</p>	<p>×</p>	<p>Many offline activities particularly delivered offline and at high schools. There were also rounds of consultations. Multiple pedagogical techniques were used to achieve “numerical citizenship”.</p>	<p>×</p>	<p>✓This is a very top-bottom pedagogy oriented media literacy training policy. It mostly aims to reach adolescents including high-school students. It uses offline methods. The policy appears to be very centralised. It is not too clear how effective this would be at the face of</p>

	intellectual property and access to media content out of cultural industries in the era of informatics.	been actively involved in raising literacy and working with the youth.				ever changing fake news scene.
Germany	○ measures are the responsibility of federal states, not of the FRG	○ there is no single authority (but the various national and federal broadcasters)	○ again, no single unitary funding instrument discernible, instead extremely heterogenous scene of public funders	○ impossible to answer as media literacy “not the responsibility” of public broadcasters; broadcasters do engage in relevant initiatives on voluntary basis	✗	There are numerous initiatives run by regional public broadcasters and addressing children and teenagers, but these are not covered by AVMSD
Finland	✓ The Act on Audiovisual Programmes and a national media literacy policy, published by the Ministry of	✓ The report details the roles of the Ministry of Education and	✓ Since 2015, the Ministry of Education and Culture has actively granted	✓ Finland demonstrates active engagement and awareness-	○ Carries out collective assessment of the activities and uses	Media education and media literacy is a cross-sectorial effort in Finland. Media literacy is

	<p>Education and Culture, actively promote and develop comprehensive legal measures for enhancing media literacy skills.</p> <p>The Act on Audiovisual Programmes (2012) and the National Media Literacy Policy (2019) outline their visions, goals, and proposals for media education with a central aim: to enhance Finland's overall media literacy across all demographics</p>	<p>Culture and the National Audiovisual Institute (KAVI) in promoting media literacy, highlighting cross-sectoral efforts and collaboration among various stakeholders</p>	<p>special financial support—initially amounting to 524,000 euros—for the promotion of media education and media literacy; however, subsequent rounds witnessed a decline in these grants: culminating in an unprecedented low by 2022 with only €175,000 allocated.</p>	<p>raising efforts, such as Media Literacy Week, Finnish Game Week, and various educational seminars and workshops.</p>	<p>different methods to assess the effectiveness of the activities. Runs annual highlights and survey data for the assessment of the Media Literacy Week, but also acknowledges the challenges in evaluating media literacy as an individual subject due to its integration into broader activities</p>	<p>often carried out as part of a broader set of activities and the evaluation is made accordingly, not usually as an individual subject or task</p>
Italy	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Digital and media literacy initiatives

			<p>collaborative initiatives such as the call for proposals for national education projects on image education and audience training, further support media literacy efforts are noteworthy.</p>	<p>collaborative practice are noteworthy between Digital Media Observatory and AGCOM (Communications Regulatory Authority) to combat misinformation and promote media literacy and Department for Youth Policies and Civil Service under the Ministry of Sport and Youth focuses on media literacy and safe new media usage.</p>	<p>Initiatives targeting media literacy have engaged students and teachers from primary, lower secondary, and upper secondary schools across Italy, sometimes extending involvement to parents. The initiatives have primarily focused on youth aged 6-14 and individuals over 55, with occasional targeting of corporate employees, content creators, or</p>	<p>are heterogeneous. It would be necessary to have a common framework to guide operators and enhance recognition and impact evaluation. The recent legislative framework offers initial guidance, with ongoing institutional collaboration between MIMIT and AGCOM for further promotion of media literacy initiatives.</p>
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					specific viewer categories.	
Slovenia	☐ <p>Highlights that the republic of Slovenia will fund the Ministry responsible for the media</p>	☐ <p>The Agency for communication Networks and services is responsible for implementing media literacy projects</p>	✘	✓	✘	Content on media and information literacy are published on their MiPi Media and Literacy portal in which their objective is to protect end users of electronic communications by using communication platforms such as Facebook and Instagram.
Hungary	☒ <p>The media laws in Hungary are covered by the National Media and Communications Authority (NMHH), the</p>	☒ <p>The Media Council acts as an overseeing body for media services in the country. the primary task of</p>	☐	✘	✘	The Hungarian digital literacy policy and tools are geared towards protecting children from what is politically considered as the adverse effects of the internet. Digital

	<p>Media Services Directive, and the 2010 (CLXXXV) Act on Media Services and Mass Communications. There is also a separate public body called the Media Council, which oversees the operations of the media outlets in Hungary.</p>	<p>the Media Council is to ensure the legitimate functioning of the democratic public in the media. Furthermore, the Media Council has the authority to establish guidelines and rules regarding the protection of children from harmful contents in the media, while the NMHH takes on media literacy and online education projects and activities in the country</p>				<p>harm as a concept is merely operationalised to protect children and the government has introduced many programmes to this extent. There is one singular programme directed for the elderly. The government has established expansive networks with the third sector and universities to deliver these programmes. However, there is a procedure for audit and independent accountability. Moreover, using media literacy as a tool to recognise fake news, disinformation and similar related content that may</p>
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						boost extremism is missing.
Poland	<p>✓ Poland has established comprehensive legal and policy measures for media education, detailed in the Broadcasting Act. These measures involve both public broadcasters and video-sharing platform providers (VSPs) with specific obligations to promote media literacy.</p> <p>References: (Article 6(2)(13) of the Broadcasting Act). Directive 2018/1808 of Polish Law. (Article</p>	<p>✓ The report indicates that the Broadcasting Act (Article 6(2)(13)-(14)) indicates a cooperation between NBC and other state bodies, non-governmental organisations and other institutions in the field of media education to compliance with obligations imposed on audio-visual media service providers and VSPs. Various institutions and</p>	<p>○ No funds dedicated exclusively for media education, however, the media education activities are financed from the general budget of the organisation.</p>	<p>✓ Poland actively implements the National Security Strategy of the Republic (2020) by engaging in an extensive array of activities such as educational programs, workshops, and campaigns across multiple platforms for varying age groups. This strategy underscores efforts to enhance public awareness regarding threats and information manipulation through robust education initiatives; it also advocates for</p>	<p>✓ The report indicates that NBC is responsible for evaluating and monitoring the activities of implementation of media. The main reason stated for the ongoing assessment of the implementation is to protect user standards. The report shows that none of the providers under Polish jurisdiction has yet fulfilled all the relevant requirements of the</p>	<p>Poland stands out for its notable efforts in combating disinformation, particularly within the recent context of geopolitical events and the COVID-19 pandemic. The #FakeHunter project and other public awareness campaigns demonstrate an active approach to tackle contemporary challenges in media literacy. Responding to Ukraine invasion-related disinformation, on both 24 February and 4 March, the National Broadcasting Council (NBC) took decisive action by</p>

	21(1a)(11)). (Art. 21(2)(10)).	bodies also carry out tasks in media education, demonstrating a structured approach to organizational measures. References: Declaration on Cooperation in the Field of Media Education: signed on 17 November 2002 by representatives of the National Broadcasting Council, the Chancellery of the Prime Minister (Digitisation), the Ministry of Culture and National Heritage, the		knowledge promotion along with good practices development towards fostering a well-informed society resilient against cyber-security challenges.	Broadcasting Act. Furthermore, the majority of VSP platform providers do not yet use the relevant graphic symbols set out in the NBC regulation issued under Article 47p(3) of the Broadcasting Act	excluding several channels, including Russia Today and RT Documentary among others from its register; this move signifies a strong commitment towards addressing misinformation effectively. This action reflects Poland's commitment to combating misinformation amid geopolitical tensions.
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		Ministry of Education and Science, the National Film Archive – Audio-visual Institute, the Ombudsman for Children’s Rights, the Polish Press Agency, the Digitisation Council, the Scientific and the Academic Computer Network NASK.				
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2.3. Summary of section two.

The summary of media literacy and digital education efforts across multiple countries underscores the diversity in approaches and initiatives. In Austria, there's a focus on legal amendments and organisational measures, with basic digital education integrated into school curricula. Germany exhibits decentralised responsibilities, predominantly driven by broadcasters rather than a centralised authority. Meanwhile, Finland displays cross-sectorial efforts where media literacy is integrated into broader activities and assessed accordingly. France focuses on legislation to reduce harmful content in the traditional and online media, while promotes media literacy in schools. Italy emphasises collaborative initiatives aimed at combating misinformation and targeting various demographics. In Slovenia, there's an emphasis on governmental funding and organisational roles, particularly in safeguarding users through communication platforms. However, Hungary and Poland mention media literacy efforts without providing comprehensive details on evaluation methods and key areas of focus. While in Hungary, there is no emphasis on the transparency to the public funding of the media, there is, however, a focus on media literacy training and online education projects in both Poland and Hungary.

3. Evaluation of Nonformal Education Tools:

Focus has been given to nonformal media and information literacy initiatives operating in youth work, particularly Erasmus+ and ESC projects and initiatives listed on the SALTO PI¹⁵ Youth site and in the report by Lopez et al., (2022)¹⁶. The objective of the report by Lopez et.al. was to conduct an analysis aimed at exploring the approaches to Media and Information Literacy (MIL) initiatives within the European youth sector. The purpose of this (D.Rad) report is to evaluate the range of non-formal initiatives

¹⁵ Salto Participation and Information - <https://participationpool.eu/>

¹⁶ Salto *Media and Information Literacy in the EU Youth Programmes: Empowering Youth Participation report*.<https://participationpool.eu/resource/report-media-information-literacy-in-the-eu-youth-programmes-empowering-youth-participation/>

dedicated to enhancing media and information literacy (MIL) skills across D.Rad nations, with a particular emphasis on addressing the risks associated with online radicalisation as highlighted in D.Rad reports D5.1, D6.2 and D7.1).

3.1 Comparative Analysis: Thematic Points in the EU General Guide vs. Salto Country Reports

This section summarises youth engagement through Media and Information Literacy (MIL) training in EU Youth Programmes with a particular focus on the findings from the Salto PI report (Lopez et al., 2022). The report reviews MIL initiatives, trends, and requirements within the Erasmus+ and European Solidarity Corps Youth Programmes in 2021, findings from which suggest that integrating MIL with other key topics is essential to effectively implement MIL training within existing programmes (Lopez et al., 2022). Findings from the study also emphasise numerous direct correlations between MIL and youth participation projects. Specifically, instances were identified where MIL intersects with online engagement, critical thinking, involvement of youth minorities, and utilisation of new media and information technologies.

The evaluation of MIL training initiatives and activities within Erasmus+ and European Solidarity Corps projects reveal a measure of alignment with the guidelines set forth by the EU Commission, particularly concerning specified criteria d) and e) below. However, it should be noted that the EC MIL guidelines¹⁷ make reference to MIL training in formal education settings, rather the nonformal settings referenced in the Erasmus and ESC initiatives.

d) Engagement and awareness raising activities, including media literacy curricula: *promote and develop media literacy skills across all age groups, both in formal education and in lifelong learning contexts; establish communication channels with the national hubs of the European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO); measures to promote and develop media*

¹⁷ [Media Literacy Guidelines I Shaping Europe's digital future \(europa.eu\)](https://european-council.europa.eu/media/en/press-communications/infographic/infographic-media-literacy-guidelines-1-shaping-europe-s-digital-future)

literacy skills in formal educational curricula at different levels – including modules for teacher training; Make reference to any relevant media literacy resources available to the public.

e. Evaluation Measures and Methods *Implement measures to evaluate the impact of regional or national media initiatives; Focus on Performance Measurement Indicators; Reporting Requirement (measures and impact); Document Outcomes (to share best practice)¹⁸. Member States have the option to employ recognised evaluation frameworks in order to measure media literacy levels.*

Following the directive outlined in point e), the Lopez report and the Salto PI website serve as repositories for exemplary practices. The Salto website, in particular, offers an extensive compilation of resources and case studies showcasing nonformal education's best practices, spanning various levels of Media and Information Literacy (MIL) across subject areas such as critical thinking, digital citizenship and digital well-being comprehension. Following an evaluation of the Erasmus+ and Nevertheless, while a significant portion of initiatives incorporated MIL components, the comprehensive analysis unveiled a common shortfall: across all projects surveyed, MIL initiatives constituted less than 40% of the total project count. This suggests both

MIL Representation Across Erasmus+ Key Actions and ESC Solidarity projects

	% of ERASMUS+ MIL projects in 2021					% of ESC MIL projects in 2021
	KA152-YOU: Mobility of young people	KA153-YOU: Mobility of youth workers	KA154-YOU: Youth participation activities	KA210-YOU: Small-scale partnerships in youth	KA220-YOU: Cooperation partnerships in youth	
Number of MIL projects	150	100	64	25	20	175
% of MIL from total number of projects	21.9 %	29.8 %	34.6 %	28.7 %	35.7 %	20.3 %
Digital skills and competences	32.5 %	27.3 %	22.4 %	17.6 %	21.4 %	43.5 %
Digital content, technologies and practices	17.5 %	16.1 %	2.6 %	17.6 %	17.9 %	no data
Media literacy and tackling disinformation	15.5 %	9.1 %	15.8 %	2.9 %	3.6 %	8.6 %
Digital youth work	7 %	30.1 %	11.8 %	38.2 %	39.3 %	14.4 %
Digital safety	8 %	4.2 %	6.6 %	0 %	7.1 %	7.2 %
Information and communication technologies (ICT)	7 %	6.3 %	3.9 %	0 %	7.1 %	7.7 %
Digital literacy, information, constructive dialogue, fake news	12.5 %	7 %	36.8 %	23.5 %	3.6 %	18.7 %

¹⁸ Members states are also encouraged to share and exchange information and best practice in the context of ERGA (European Regulators Group for Audiovisual Media Services <https://erga-online.eu/>)

presence of MIL initiatives within these programs, and the scope for further enhancement, to ensure a more robust integration of MIL principles across a broader spectrum of projects. Such findings underscore the importance of fortifying MIL efforts within educational and youth-focused initiatives to empower individuals with the critical skills necessary to navigate the complexities of the modern information landscape effectively (see Figure 2).

Figure 2 MIL Representation across Erasmus+ and ESC programmes (see Lopez et al., 2022)

Although the non-formal educational tools examined within Erasmus+ and ESC projects did not always directly correspond to explicit key points across the national guidelines, various facets outlined in the guidelines were implicitly reflected in the initiatives. When exploring the perspectives of youth stakeholders regarding MIL, survey data from the study presented a unanimous consensus on prioritising the requirements of the target audience as stipulated in the ERGA media literacy Report¹⁹. Given the diversity among

“..participation, critical thinking, engaging youth minorities, and working with new media and information technologies”
(Lopez et al., 2022:13)

users, MIL measures understood as crucial included the need cater to varying needs and abilities while also considering their socio-cultural factors. In order to recognise the unique characteristics and demands of individuals and groups, it was recommended that MIL skills should be cultivated through a dual approach: both by actively engaging with existing content and by empowering youths to create their own, was understood as key areas of MIL. This multifaceted strategy ensures that individuals not only consume media critically but also develop the capacity to produce responsible and informed content themselves (both key areas of the EC guidelines).

¹⁹ ERGA Media Literacy Report Recommendations for key principles, best practices and a Media Literacy Toolbox for Video-sharing Platforms. Section 2.3 Focus of User/Citizen p 15- <https://erga-online.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/ERGA-AG3-2021-Report-on-Media-Literacy.pdf>

Moreover, fostering collaboration between experts in priority areas and MIL was

“The ability to put media into use in an ethical and quality way gives people more power to be fairly represented, tell their own stories and initiate positive changes.”
(Lopez et al., 2022:13)

thought to produce outcomes that align more closely with the current priorities of EU Youth Programmes, adapt to the constantly evolving MIL landscape, and cater to the needs of the youth work community in Europe. The report contends that improving the efficiency and pertinence of MIL initiatives can be achieved by tackling the evolving challenges encountered by youth in the digital era such as the risks involved in the use of interactive media, gaming and apps. Moreover, the report discusses the need for proficiency in locating, critically assessing, and analysing information, and stresses the imperative

nature of users of digital technology knowing how (and why) to ethically utilise *and* generate media across civic engagement and democratic societies. These competencies are vital for fostering a more equitable and inclusive information landscape and are visible across many of the youth initiatives. Empowering individuals to use digital media responsibly enables them to advocate for fair representation, share their narratives, and instigate constructive societal transformations.

Furthermore, the initiatives presented in the report highlight the importance of strengthening children's and young people's critical thinking and media literacy skills - empowering them to make sound judgement on, and to overcome, the ever-present threats of fake news, cyber bullying, radicalisation, cybersecurity threats and fraud.

3.3 Interconnection between youth participation and MIL projects

The report shines a light on the important and relevant link between Youth Participation and Media and Information Literacy (MIL) projects, particularly focusing on the role of critical thinking as a common element between the two. Across both Erasmus+ and European Solidarity Corps (ESC) youth participation projects (YPP) are initiatives that involve young people in various aspects of decision-making, community development, or social change processes.

Figure 1: Connection between Youth Participation & MIL
Lopez et al., 2022:9

‘..critical thinking’ as the transversal-horizontal competence that is relevant and often present in both kinds of projects
(Lopez et al., 2022: 9)

These initiatives aim to empower young individuals to have voice and influence in matters that affect them and their communities. MIL projects across the same organisational settings, focus on equipping individuals with the skills and competencies to critically analyse, evaluate, and create media and information in various forms - enhancing young people's ability to navigate the vast amounts of information available in today's digital age and to become responsible consumers and creators of media content.

In this context, critical thinking was described as a "transversal-horizontal competence²⁰," meaning it is a skill that cuts across different domains or fields. In the context of both Youth Participation and MIL projects, critical thinking was deemed essential for effectively engaging with information, ideas, and decision-making processes. Furthermore, critical thinking was relevant and often present in both Youth

²⁰ “Transversal-horizontal competencies” are skills that aren't tied to a singular job, task, academic field, or area of expertise, and are applicable across various situations and professional environments, such as organisational skills.

Participation and MIL projects. In Youth Participation projects, critical thinking as a taught skill was understood as implicit rather than explicitly stated. However, it played a significant role in the needs analysis and in fostering alternative methodologies and methods to address the challenges or issues being tackled by projects. Even where critical thinking was not explicitly mentioned in Youth Participation projects, it was implied through the approach taken to address issues and empower young people. The youth leaders in all probability gave great reflection to the difficulties that young people face, and the methodologies employed to tackle these challenges were

observed to promote the development of critical thinking skills. Overall, the report highlights the interconnectedness of critical thinking skills development with both Youth Participation and MIL projects, underpinning the importance of nurturing these skills among young people to empower them as active participants in their communities and as responsible consumers and creators of media and information.

Identifying Gaps and Deficiencies in Media Literacy

- Erasmus+

Some deficiencies were acknowledged within the thematic areas of 'digital safety,' 'Information and communication Technologies (ICT),' and 'media literacy and addressing misinformation.' Based on the data provided, there is a notable absence of data on digital safety and ICT within one of the smaller projects.

- European Solidarity Corps

Digital safety, and digital content, technologies, & practices were the two thematic areas that notably lack sufficient knowledge or attention. Data regarding projects focused on the aspect of '*Digital content, technologies, and practices*' within MIL was absent. Furthermore, according to the report, only every fifth project (on the ESC website) is related to MIL (20.3%), rendering the ESC program less enriched of the two EU Programs in MIL. However, *Digital Skills and Competencies* emerged as the predominant thematic area within ESC Solidarity projects *and* those falling under Erasmus+ KA152-YOU: *Mobility of Young People*. Furthermore, this theme

represents the largest subset of *all* MIL-focused projects across both EU Programs, accounting for 23.4% or 125 out of 534 projects (see figure 2/p22).

The Salto report highlights areas of proficiency and need within the following areas that relate to digital competencies and safety (see tables 3 and 4).

1. Media & Information Literacy (Media & Its Impact, Quality of Information, News Literacy, Information Disorder, Social Media, Library Literacy,
2. Critical Thinking
3. Content Creation Digital content, technologies, and practices (including ethical practices)
4. Media literacy and tackling disinformation.
5. Digital safety (data protection, cyber bullying, digital security)
6. Information and communication technologies (ICT)
7. Media and Participation – Human Rights Education & Gender Equality, Radicalisation, Hate speech
8. Digital Literacy, information, constructive dialogue and fake news

- The online survey had a question on which of the MIL topic areas the participants find is being covered sufficiently in the projects throughout 2020-2021. The options and the vote distribution is shown in the chart below:

Table 3 Topic areas the participants find is being covered sufficiently in the projects throughout 2020-2021 Lopez et al., 2022 p.46

Using the similar logic, the results showed the MIL areas that the survey participants found least covered by the youth projects:

Table 4. topic areas the participants find is being least covered in the projects. Lopez et al., 2022, p.47.

3.4. Evaluating the facets of Media and Information Literacy (MIL) concerning D.Rad nations in addressing the perils linked with online radicaliation.

Disinformation and Radicalisation concerns

In recent times, our global communities have been grappling with significant social crises, notably the COVID-19 pandemic, the conflict in Ukraine and the current crisis in Palestine and Israel. These events have created an environment where misinformation and disinformation thrive, leaving individuals vulnerable to being misinformed or misled. In such a climate, it becomes imperative to equip young people and those working with youth with the necessary MIL skills to enable their meaningful participation in society. The diverse array of media exposure significantly influences cognitive outcomes, such as emotions, attitudes, perceptions, and behaviours. (Wolfowicz1 et al., 2022), and efforts must be undertaken to counteract the spread of online or digital radicalisation, hate speech, cyber-bullying and the marginalisation of individuals from democratic engagement. Additionally, there is an increasing trend

where radical groups utilise video games as a platform for indoctrination and recruitment purposes (Wolfowicz et al., 2022). The escalation of online dangers emphasises the pressing need for guidance in prioritising focus areas for the future, notably in navigating the expansive and diverse media landscape. Unfortunately, NGOs frequently face challenges due to insufficient understanding, guidelines, and sustainable strategies despite their noble intentions.

Table 5 offers a comparative breakdown of Erasmus+ and ESC projects offering digital youth training in D.Rad countries that encompass strategies and training that counteract the risks of online radicalisation.

Table 5: ERASMUS+ & ESC Thematic areas of Youth Training across D.Rad countries)

D.RAD COUNTRIES	PROJECT TITLE	MEDIA LITERACY	DIGITAL SAFETY & DISINFORMATION	CRITICAL THINKING	SOCIAL INCLUSION & DEMOCRACY	EDUCATION & EMPLOYABILITY	TARGET GROUP	ADDITIONAL NOTES OF INTEREST
<p>GERMANY GEORGIA TURKEY</p> <p>Also non-D.Rad countries - Armenia Sweden</p>	<p><i>ECODING – New Technologies for Environment, Employability & Civic Activism</i></p> <p>Link Erasmus+</p>	<p>YES</p> <p>Clear skills in aspects of MIL – programming, coding, robotics and coupled these with issues of cyber security etc</p>	<p>To some extents (cyber security, AI and surveillance systems)</p>	<p>YES, to an extent through exploring activism, climate change & and the environment</p>	<p>To some extent though dialogue focusing on social activism, climate change and the environment. Embracing inclusivity & democracy enhances the effectiveness of social activism by addressing systemic inequalities and promoting solidarity among various communities.</p>	<p>YES – core digital skills, creating website, apps and toolbox increase levels of employability</p>	<p>Youth</p>	<p>The project facilitated MIL skills and integrated them with facets of social activism and employability. It motivated users to develop a website/app and digital toolbox, thereby enhancing their employability. These acquired skills also heightened awareness of issues such as cybersecurity and critical thinking.</p>

<p>ITALY SERBIA FRANCE</p>	<p><i>EduAction Radio goes International</i> <i>Erasmus +</i> link</p>	<p>Some medial literacy skills – in the form of creating a community digital radio and podcast and other short digital products – video, infographics</p>	<p>Yes, to some level, attendees learned about responsible processing of information and distinguishing between real sources and fake ones</p>	<p>Yes, implicitly through dialogue sharing on topics focussed in their created video and podcasts</p>	<p>Yes – the project engagement aimed to foster a sense of belonging within the community while also encouraging connection with the EU and promoting "participation for all." Additional learning opportunities were provided, focusing on mental health and well-being, as well as promoting a sustainable green Europe.</p>	<p>To some extent, by boosting confidence, concentrating directly on four European Youth Goals, and fostering self awareness while acquiring digital skills</p>	<p>Young people – socially disadvantaged 13-30 year olds</p>	<p>Participants learned the importance of copyright and plagiarism but clearly defining sources in their created outputs</p>
<p>AUSTRIA POLAND</p> <p>Also other non-D.Rad countries – Croatia, Bulgaria, Spain & Romania</p>	<p><i>Think Before you Click</i> <i>Erasmus+</i> Link</p>	<p>Yes – the project fostered critical thinking, media literacy, and social media literacy skills among the participants. Through this,</p>	<p>Yes – identified as one of the project's main themes. Participants developed skills through the in-practice learning of responsible content creation – and links to counter disinformation</p>	<p>Yes – as identified in previous columns.</p>	<p>Participants engaged with local people, particularly local youth, both in person and through online gatherings with communities from other partner regions. Additionally,</p>	<p>Yes – in an implicit manner through the various skills development</p>	<p>Local young people</p>	<p>Main focus of project was to provide participants with the necessary tools to assist their youth in digital development. The project encouraged participants to</p>

		they cultivated a positive relationship with technology, particularly social media platforms.			local workshops were organised in various communities.			develop critical thinking, media literacy, and social media literacy skills.
<p>ITALY</p> <p>FINLAND</p> <p>TURKEY</p> <p>(also no-D.Rad countries – Romania, Netherlands)</p>	<p><i>Media Detox</i></p> <p><i>Erasmus+</i></p> <p>Link</p>	Yes	Yes, to an extent by exploring how mass media functions and its influence on public thinking.	Yes Participants were encouraged examine the ways in which media messages influence the levels of tolerance or intolerance in our societies, particularly in relation to the migrant and refugee crisis.	Yes, to an extent, particularly in relation to migrant and refugee issues	The initiative promoted innovative practices, participatory management methods, and open educational resources.	Youth workers	Participants in the project gained insight into the functioning of mass media and its influence on social cohesion, and explored essential elements of trustworthy journalism, with a critical mindset.
<p>ITALY</p> <p>(-other non-D.Rad countries – Spain, Estonia, Romania & Bulgaria)</p>	<p><i>Photographing the R's (recycle, reuse, reduce)</i></p> <p>*ERASMUS+</p> <p>Link</p>	Digital skills development through the use of photography	NO	YES, through the use of photography with topics covering resource scarcity & toxic waste accumulation around the world	YES, through skills topics of Creativity, arts & culture, Environment and Climate change	YES, education and awareness of global and local environmental problems	Young People,	Project led to wider projects being replicated in other geographical areas

<p>Italy</p> <p>Also non D.Rad countries – Slovakia, Spain and Cyprus</p>	<p><i>Turn on the brain – new methods and games for building etiquette on the internet.</i></p> <p>Erasmus+</p> <p>Link</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>Yes, to an extent – resilience to online marketing disinformation.</p>	<p>Critical thinking through research and innovation training activities</p>	<p>Aspects of social inclusion and democracy are essential for advancing the principles of the key components of this project - "recycle, reuse, reduce" by ensuring equal participation, fostering community engagement, and promoting accountable decision-making processes in sustainable waste management efforts In particular, the project aimed to develop training manuals for young people with fewer opportunities</p>	<p>Educational programme & innovative training</p>	<p>Youth workers</p>	<p>The project aimed to develop innovative methods and games targeted at young people, particularly those facing fewer opportunities. It resulted in the creation of a new educational program and training manual designed to address the challenges posed by disinformation websites and networks.</p>
<p>GERMANY</p> <p>Also, non-D.Rad countries – Sweden, Spain, Romania</p>	<p><i>Combating social media disinformation among youth through live action role play</i></p>	<p>Yes - Equip youth workers with pedagogical tools and resources to</p>	<p>Yes - methods and tools for increasing MIL skills to ultimately reduce</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>Yes, to an extent through inclusive & democratic participation.</p>	<p>Yes (education) Project aims to provide youth educators</p>	<p>Youth Workers-aiding youth workers to support young people</p>	<p>The project developed innovative and participatory tools and</p>

	Erasmus+ Link	boost MIL efficiency in young people they work with.	disinformation on social media.		Promoting digital literacy programs that are accessible to all demographics helps empower individuals to critically evaluate information online and become more resilient to disinformation campaigns	with the necessary pedagogical resources to develop, among young people, the skills and competences to identify and tackle online disinformation.		methods that were relevant to young people – and that were useable in follow-up projects. Projects included role play activity via mobile phones, toolkits, and manual/guide.
Poland	<i>Mamy tak samo</i> European Solidarity Corps Link	Media literacy skills	Targeting disinformation and digital safety	Yes, to an extent through self reflection of own and peer group experiences	Offering specialist and peer support & friendship while strengthening interests of the community and the role of woman and mothers in the community	Peer to peer skills sharing and developing personal aspirations.	Young women and mothers	Online peer support events offering shared experiences, and professional guidance. Furthermore, the project elevated community awareness of loneliness, It also reinforced the roles of

								women and mothers within the community, establishing a platform for sustained collaboration among them.
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5. Assessing the Impact of EU Media Literacy Directive and Informal Tools on Online Digital Identity and Radicalisation: Comparative report of findings from D.5.5, D6.2 and D7.1

Findings from D.Rad reports highlight the significance of comprehending the influence of online group identity in radicalisation processes (D7.1²¹), along with the practical requirements of governmental bodies and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) in tackling online radicalisation (D6.2²²). The findings from these reports corroborate our evaluation of the effectiveness of the EU media literacy directive, as well as informal media literacy initiatives. They shed light on the efforts made both formally and informally at the EU level in addressing this issue, and the limitations within the complexities of addressing risks of online radicalisation.

As digital connectivity increases, there have been concerns regarding increased isolation and individualism as people negotiate new meanings of self and communities. Sherry Turkle (2011) has discussed fears that people immerse themselves in virtual worlds, isolating themselves to the point of being physically present in one space, yet mentally and emotionally engaged elsewhere. While this may be true for some avid users of digital media, it must also be acknowledged that the capacity for online digital connections to transcend space and time boundaries can be said to have contributed to the lengthening and deepening of social connectivity across the globe, and while this can be a source of good in that various social media platforms shape the sharing process through offering apps that allow families and friends to show that they are safe during events such as the Paris bombing or incidents of natural disaster, or more recently, the Covid pandemic, online communities can, on the other hand, act as echo chambers where people gather to listen to views from ‘people like us’. This can be especially true within the online presence of more secret

²¹ D7.1 A social psychological perspective on trends of radicalisation: <https://dradproject.com/?publications=a-social-psychological-perspective-on-trends-of-radicalisation>

²² D6.2 AI and (De)Radicalisation Interaction Study <https://dradproject.com/?publications=ai-and-deradicalisation-interaction-study>

or closed extreme radicalisation and hate groups where the sharing of views is accompanied by the sharing of skills: ‘to produce their own “alternative media” but also to recruit and train like-minded individuals’²³

D7.1 identifies the significance of group identity as a crucial aspect of personal meaning, identity, and belonging. Online groups and communities can provide a space where individuals with similar interests or experiences can unite, exchange resources, and extend emotional support. In times of personal difficulty, humans are inclined to seek ways to alleviate feelings of insecurity, whether concerning identity or belonging, and may find themselves drawn to affiliating with a group that offers distinct norms and values that are appealing to their own (Hogg et al., 2013; Rolon et al., 2024).

While social networks can provide positive social support, validate narratives, and reinforce normative societal behaviours aimed at specific goals, our D.Rad findings shed light on the role of online spaces in radicalisation and the proliferation of extremist beliefs²⁴. Individuals engaging in radical extremism increasingly utilise the Internet to share content, notably through platforms like Tik Tok (Weimann & Masri, 2023), (also reported by D.Rad reports D5.1²⁵), but also increasing through apps and gaming platforms ((Wolfowicz1 et al., 2022)) Here, they offer content customised for their audiences’ demographic, and while the substance may

Figure 6 Lopez et al., 2022

²³ D.Rad report D5.1 (Ferenczi et al, 2021:5) <https://dradproject.com/?publications=cultural-drivers-of-radicalisation-in-the-uk>

²⁴ D7.1: A social psychological perspective on trends of radicalisation <https://dradproject.com/d7-1-country-reports-social-psychology/>

²⁵ D5.1 Cultural Drivers of radicalisation <https://dradproject.com/reports/d5-1-visual-radicalisation/>

remain consistent, the presentation varies, so that the language used appeals to younger audiences. These findings underscore the necessity for providing alternative methods to help young people understand online content effectively and for providing education on digital safety and recognising toxic content²⁶.

“media and the media representation of minorities can directly impact politics, tolerance and societal narratives.....”

Figure 7 Lopez et al., 2022

Furthermore, the portrayal of minorities in the media holds significant sway over political landscapes, societal attitudes, and narratives of tolerance. This influence highlights the pivotal role of media in shaping public perceptions and fostering inclusivity. However, the power of media representation comes with a caveat: without the capacity to critically assess and effectively utilise digital technologies, their impact may veer toward detrimental outcomes or fail to generate meaningful societal progress. Therefore, fostering media and information literacy is essential to harnessing the potential of digital platforms for constructive social change and mitigating the risks of misinformation and polarisation as highlighted in D.Rad reports D5.1, D6.2 and D 7.1.

6. Conclusion: Evaluating Successes and Pinpointing Areas for Improvement.

Data from national reports and nonformal educational tools are synthesised to assess compliance to EU guidelines.

²⁶ D6.2: AI and (De)Radicalisation Interaction Study - <https://dradproject.com/?publications=ai-and-deradicalisation-interaction-study>

Both National Reports and nonformal initiatives showcase a diverse range of approaches, displaying some discrepancies in content, structure, and interpretation of the guidelines. It is unclear whether nonformal initiatives are developed following the EU guidelines, or whether they take guidance from Resource Centres such as Salto PI²⁷/Salto -Youth²⁸

Developing a comprehensive framework for media information literacy is necessary to provide guidance to European Union (EU) member states. Such a framework would not only serve as a blueprint for fostering critical thinking and digital literacy skills among citizens of all ages, but would also facilitate an evaluation of its effectiveness and impact. Establishing a unified approach across EU nations, helps to ensure consistency in formal and non-formal education and awareness initiatives aimed at navigating the complexities of contemporary media landscapes.

Developing a comprehensive framework for media information literacy is imperative to provide guidance to European Union (EU) member states, and NGO's. Such a framework not only serves as a blueprint for fostering critical thinking and digital literacy skills among citizens but also facilitates the evaluation of its effectiveness and impact. By establishing a unified approach across EU nations, initiatives can ensure consistency in non-formal; and formal education and awareness programs aimed at navigating the complexities of contemporary media landscapes.

This framework should encompass various dimensions, including but not limited to:

Curriculum Integration: There should be continued incorporation of media literacy into formal education systems, from primary to tertiary levels, to provide learners with vital skills in distinguishing credible information from misinformation and disinformation.

Teacher Training: Governments should endeavour to provide educators with specialised training and resources to proficiently teach media literacy skills,

²⁷ <https://www.salto-youth.net/rc/participation/>

²⁸ <https://www.salto-youth.net/about/>

empowering them to mentor students in responsibly analysing, evaluating, and creating media content.

Public Awareness Campaigns: Governments and NGO's should be encouraged to initiate focused campaigns to increase public understanding of the significance of media literacy, alongside offering practical guidance on recognising misinformation across various media channels.

Collaboration with Media Outlets: Nations should continue to partner with media organisations to uphold ethical journalism standards, transparency, and accountability, while also fostering alliances to ensure the dissemination of accurate information.

Digital Tools and Resources: Funding should be made available to allow the development and distribution of digital tools and resources, including fact-checking websites, browser extensions, and educational materials, to simplify information verification and counteract the proliferation of misinformation online. These efforts should encompass both formal and informal digital training programs.

Research and Evaluation: Promote (and utilise) continuous research to evaluate the impact of media literacy interventions, recognise emerging trends and challenges in the media landscape, and adapt strategies accordingly.

International Collaboration: Both, nations and NGO's, should continue to Participate in cross-border partnerships and knowledge-sharing endeavours with other regions and international organisations to exchange best practices and utilize collective expertise in promoting media literacy worldwide.

By implementing a comprehensive framework that includes these components, EU member states and NGOs can strengthen their joint endeavours to promote media literacy, encourage informed citizenship, and mitigate the adverse effects of misinformation on society. Furthermore, ongoing evaluation and improvement of this framework is vital for adjusting to changing media dynamics and ensuring its sustained effectiveness.

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